

The Impact of Whistle Blowing on Economic Growth in Nigeria

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This study examined the impact of whistleblowing on economic growth in Nigeria. Whistle blowing was proxied by recovery of looted funds, while economic growth was proxied by Gross Domestic Product and Human Development Index. Two hypotheses were developed for this study. The expo-factor research design was adopted for the study. The sample period is 20 years from 2003-2022 and relies on secondary data collected from key agencies in Nigeria such as the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission, the Independent Corrupt Practices Commission, the Code of Conduct Bureau, Central Bank of Nigeria, National Bureau of Statistics, and International organizations such as World Bank, IMF, UNDP, among others. The econometric view (E-view) was used to analyze the transformed data. The ordinary least square was adopted for hypothesis testing. Findings for the study showed that recovery of looted funds has a positive and significant relationship with Gross Domestic Product. Moreso, recovery of looted funds has a negative but significant relationship with Human Development Index. Based on these findings, the study recommends that: Policymakers should consider strategies to mitigate these potential negative effects, such as ensuring recovered funds are effectively and efficiently reinvested into the economy to support growth and development. Furthermore, efforts should be made by the Government to enhance human development in Nigeria by involving a multifaceted approach beyond just recovering looted funds.

Keywords: Whistle Blowing; Recovered Funds; Gross Domestic Product; Human Development Index

INTRODUCTION

Economically, every developing nation tends to advance its economy into an international and more developed country like that of America, the United Kingdom, and China. Most Government strives to better the lives of its citizenry through achieving a high level of economic growth and development by sustaining a balance of payment, price stability, and full employment (Orlu, Isukul & Odiche, 2021). Every country wants to achieve stable economic growth, industrial development and higher living standards for its citizens. To this end, every economy relies on fiscal policies or public financing for economic development projects and programs as a prerequisite for the achievement of these goals. Nigeria is known as the largest country in Africa, in term of the

economy (GDP) and its population size of over 180 million which also makes it the most populous country in Africa. Nigeria enjoys the advantage of its vegetation, tropical climate with other diverse ranges of crops with lots of benefits, and this shows how vital its resources are when the goal is to achieve economic development in the country (Yahaya, 2020).

Economies around the world irrespective of the region or demographic and geographic characteristics are often faced with the management of their resources which swathes the human, material, and natural resources of a country. However, the lack of effective use or utilization of these resources raises concerns, often holds the handlers of these resources to accountability and probity

(Sodiq Lateef, Olanipekun, & Babalola, 2021). As GDP represents economic growth alone and is a too narrow indicator for measuring economic development, and lately, it is being criticized for haven failed to account for and measure other aspects of development, such as life expectancy and enrolment in school. Hence, the Human Development Index (HDI) remains a broader and more comprehensive multi-composite indicator for measuring development, compared to GDP, though GDP still provides about one-third of the index (Yahaya, 2020). In view of these economic challenges, several countries try to integrate into National economics, but in Nigeria, due to the urge for corruption, funds meant for development are at risk to diversion into a private pockets.

As part of an attempt by President Buhari's led administration to fight corruption, an economic policy was put in place, known as "Whistle blowing Policy" through the Federal Ministry of Finance, where whistleblowing as an anti-corruption mechanism has proven to be effective in many parts of the world (Orlu, Isukul & Odiche, 2021). The Whistle Blowing Programme according to the Federal Ministry of Finance (FMF 2016) is designed to encourage Nigerians (anyone) with useful information about a violation of financial regulations, mismanagement of public funds and assets, financial malpractice, fraud and theft to report it. From the FMF whistle blowing programme, it is restricted to violations and abuse of financial procedures, due diligence and related offences or matters in the public sector. This narrowed perspective, may not help the private sector which is the productive aspect of Nigerian economy (Edih, 2020). However, whistle blowing is regarded as a double-edged sword because of the "other side effects" on the whistle blower (Ifejika, 2018). Whistle-blowers are constantly confronted with reprisals and retaliations from the big boss, employers and highly placed politicians in government because of no protection law. Those blowing the whistle in Nigeria are doing so on the basis of morality, public interest and however, at their peril.

Despite these challenges, the Nigerian government has recovered some looted funds within this short period of implementation (Edih, 2020). Boluwaji, Igbekoyi, Osatuyi & Azeez (2023) measured whistleblowing mechanisms by adopting reporting mechanism, protection mechanism and investigation mechanism as proxies of whistleblowing mechanism. Report by McGuinn, Rossi and Fernandes (2017) stated that whistleblower protection in the area of public procurement could, therefore, be the amount of public funds recovered, estimated amount of corrupted funds in public procurement that could potentially be identified thanks to whistleblower disclosures. For the purpose of this study, recovery of looted funds from both foreign and within Nigeria, was adopted as the proxy of whistleblowing, where proxy represents the estimated amount of public funds that could potentially be recovered from the corrupted funds.

Statement of Problem

The problem of weak economic growth in Nigeria can be traced to the fact that the country has been bedevilled with the menace of corruption over the years. According to Anthony (2019), the lack or slow economic growth in Nigeria can be attributed to the interminable pursuit among Nigerians to maintain or gain undue-advantage(s) over fellow Nigerians. This has dealt a very strong blow on the state of development in Nigeria, especially as money meant for national projects and development are diverted into personal purses. It is estimated that Nigeria may have lost over \$500 billion to graft and the looting of public treasury by government officials since independence (Taiwo, 2015). Being a developing country, Nigeria's economy may be grossly affected by the rate at which its resources are being looted and this may negate positive development (Awogu, Obilor & Maduagwuna, 2021). Fraud, forgery and corruption are baleful triplets bedeviling Africa as a continent and particularly Nigeria as a nation. These hydra monsters as many call them, have continued to reverberate within our economic lives despite severally offered scholastic solutions theoretically and practically. In the ranking of countries by Transparency International using corruption perception index (CPI), Nigeria has continued to be viewed as a country synonymous to corruption.

For instance, in 2014 Nigeria was ranked 144 out of 177 countries assessed. Also in 2015, Nigeria ranked 136 out of 167 countries assessed with a score of 26% (Lanrewaju & Dare, 2018). Corruption, according to Otite (1986), simply means "the pervasion of integrity or state of affairs through bribery, favours or moral depravity." When two or more persons have acted together to alter the structure of society or the behaviour of functionaries so as to bring about dishonest and debased situations, one may say that corruption has taken place. In addition, section 46 of the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission Act 2004 also considers corruption to include the following: non-violent criminal and illicit activity committed with the objective of earning wealth illegally either individually or in a group or organized manner thereby violating existing legislation governing the economic activities of governments and its administration and includes any form of fraud, narcotic drug trafficking, money laundering, embezzlement, bribery, looting and any form of corrupt practices, illegal arms deals, smuggling, human trafficking and child labour, illegal oil bunkering, illegal mining, tax evasion, foreign exchange malpractices including counterfeiting of currency, theft of intellectual property and piracy, open market abuse, dumping of toxic wastes and prohibited goods (Anthony, 2019). Though some successes have been made over the years, the war against corruption in Nigeria has remained largely ineffective and made worse by the nonexistence of a coordinated strategy to the many initiatives to combat corruption in the country.

Furthermore, fraud has done much harm to the Nigerian economy and the citizenry (Efiang, Inyang & Joshua, 2016; Dauda & Ameen, 2017). It erodes the public's trust, hurts investment and undermines democracy and the rule of law. It facilitates terrorism, conflict and organised crime' (Bracking, 2007). Hence, the fight against corruption should be seen as a war that must be won in order for a society to move forward (Rachagan & Kuppasamy, 2013).

One of the varitable ways to fight corruption is through the use of whistleblowing. In Nigeria, the agencies that directly track and implement the whistleblowing policy are the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), the Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) and the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB). However, extant studies by various researchers on whistleblowing such as: Edih (2020); Atagboro, & Ogoun (2023); Anthony (2019); Sodiq, Lateef, Olanipekun and Babalola (2021); Awogu, Obilor and Maduagwuna (2021); Ogbomo (2019); Orlu, Isukul, and Odiche (2021); Taiwo (2015) have failed to empirically examine the impact of whistle blowing on economic growth in Nigeria.

Furthermore, most studies in this area have theoretically been examined leaving the empirical studies hanging which have left a gap in literature which this study intends to fill. Furthermore, whistleblowing policy serves a vital function in government and business to combat recurrent fraud and corruption. When government agencies step over legal and ethical lines, whistleblowers can make these practices public knowledge, which can lead to violators being held accountable and further reduce corruption. Therefore, this study examines the impact of whistleblowing on economic growth in Nigeria.

Aims and Objectives

Generally, this study intends to examine the impact of whistleblowing on economic growth in Nigeria. Specifically, this study intends to:

1. Ascertain the impact of recovery of looted funds and gross domestic product.
2. Examine the impact of recovery of looted funds and human development index.

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: there is no significant relationship between recovery of looted funds and Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

Ho₂: there is no significant relationship between recovery of looted funds and Human Development Index (HDI).

Theoretical Framework

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) as propounded by Ajzen (1991) is of the assumption that the intention of an individual to perform a behavioural act is based on

three self-regulatory fundamental philosophies. The first of the philosophies speaks about human attitude towards individual behaviour which is often determined by the certainty of consequences of that said behaviour. The second is the subjective norm about the behaviour which is habitually determined by normative belief. The third is the perceived behavioural control which is quite determined by the confidence that resources and opportunities are available to carry out the behaviour. (Sodiq Lateef, Olanipekun, & Babalola, (2021). TPB is by far the most widely applied theory on the links between attitudes, intention and behavior, which makes it all the more surprising that whistleblowing researchers have thus far largely failed to draw upon it. TPB has already been shown to be an effective theoretical framework for predicting intentions of ethical behavior (Randall & Gibson, 1991; Chang, 1998; McMillan & Conner, 2003; Buchan, 2005). TPB assumes that beliefs about the consequences of a given behavior contribute to form the attitude toward that behavior (Park, & Blenkinsopp, 2009). The Theory of Planned Behavior seems particularly suitable for explaining whistleblowing intentions, in that it is an action performed based on a highly complex psychological process (Gundlach et al, 2003). Furthermore Ajzen's theory has been widely accepted as a tool to analyze differences between attitude and intention as well as intention and behavior.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: McGuinn, Rossi and Fernandes (2017); Awogu, Obilor & Maduagwuna, (2021)

Whistleblowing: Generally, whistleblowing is a policy by the Federal Government of Nigeria to encourage and reassure any Nigerian with useful information of looted fund, public or private by fraudulent individuals or groups in the country of protection or conceal the personal identity, if the information is revealed. It is also aimed at given confidence to citizens in raising serious concern and question on any act leading to malpractice or unethical mode. The act is capable of developing a corrupt-free society and attracting and give confidence to foreign investors (Orlu, Isukul & Odiche, 2021). A whistle-

blower is 'any person who voluntarily discloses information in good faith about a possible misconduct or violation that has occurred, is on-going, or is about to occur' (Tukur, 2016). Whistle-blowing can also be described as disclosure made by subordinate or employee to the public on immoral or illegal behaviour in an organisation (either public or private) that capable of causing harm to a third party or the public (Shaw, 2002). Therefore, a whistle-blower is a person who raises alarm about wrongdoing perpetrated in an organisational setting (Dauda, Ahmad, & Keling, 2020). In Nigeria, the agencies that directly track and implement the whistleblowing policy are the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), the Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) and the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB).

Recovery of Looted Funds: The notion of recovering stolen assets is no new phenomenon, even though discrepancies in the monies that continue to be made by criminals through corruption, fraud and other offenses and the monies recovered by law enforcement agencies remain dramatic (Adetayo, 2018). Recovery is a term used to describe the efforts by government to recover proceeds of corruption from government officials. These are resources illicitly converted and most often transferred to other jurisdictions. The sum involved can be quite staggering (Abiodun, 2011).

Economic Growth in Nigeria: Sullivan and Steven (2003) observed that the term "economic growth" refers to the increase (or growth) of a specific measure such as real national income, gross domestic product or per capita income and do not necessarily imply economic development. This definition suggests that there is difference between economic development and economic growth. Economic growth represents an increase in jobs and income in the community. It refers to the expansion in economic activity in the state. On the other hand economic development encompasses job and income growth, sustainable increase in the productivity of individuals, businesses and resources to increase the overall wellbeing of citizens and quality of life (Onyekwere, 2016).

Gross Domestic Product (GDP): GDP represents the total value of all final goods and services produced within a country's borders over a specific time period, typically a year. GDP is a widely used indicator of a country's economic performance and growth.

Human Development Index (HDI): The concept of Human Development Index (HDI) looks beyond GDP to a broader definition of well-being. It provides a composite measure of three dimensions of human development: living a long and healthy life (measured by life expectancy), being educated (measured by adult literacy and enrolment at the primary, secondary and tertiary level) and having a decent standard of living (measured by purchasing power parity, PPP, income) (Abraham &

Ahmed, 2011). Human development is the enlargement of people's choices to live more prosperous lives (Mohammed & Obilikwu 2018)

Empirical Reviews: Erin, Ogundele and Ogundele (2016) examined whistle-blowing and the quality of financial reporting in the Nigerian banking sector. The total sample size of 275 was used for the study. This study uses regression analysis method to investigate the effects of whistle-blowing on the quality of financial reporting in the Nigerian banking sector. The study used adjusted R^2 as a primary metrics for measuring the model specification. The results show that the R square, which is coefficient of determination reveal a high value for all the parameters (KPMG- 72.8%, PWC- 61.2%, Ernst & Young-58.2%, Akintola Williams Deloitte- 64.0%) in explaining the model. The empirical findings show that whistle-blowing adoption has a positive significant relationship on the quality of financial reporting in the Nigerian banking sector. Moreso, Ogbomo (2019) investigated the effectiveness of the WBW Policy in combating corruption in the Nigerian public sector. The study was carried out in Delta, Edo, Enugu, and Anambra States respectively. Data were obtained through structured questionnaire. Survey design was employed in the study. A total of one hundred and two (102) auditors and 162 accountants were sampled in the public sector. Judgmental Sampling Technique (JST) was employed in selecting the 264 respondents in the four states' public organisations. Descriptive statistical techniques such as, charts, mean, standard deviation, tables, and percentages response analysis were used in analyzing the data. Cronbach alpha coefficient was used to test for reliability of the research instrument and the result was (0.7110). The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was employed in testing the hypothesis. SPSS 23.0 was used. The results revealed that the WBW Policy is effective combating corruption in the public sector of Nigeria. The study concluded that the WBW Policy have been effective in combating corruption in the public sector. Likewise, Ibrahim, Sharfadi and Imam (2020) examined corruption and whistle blowing policy in Nigeria: gains and challenges. With this policy 2.5%- 5% incentives of the recovered fund will be given to the whistle blower. The study heavily relied on secondary sources of data from library and the internet. Further to this, social exchange theory was used as a theoretical frame of reference to link voluntary reporting of corruption with the reward attached to it. Furthermore, Okafor, Adebisi, Opara and Okafor (2020) investigated the challenges and opportunities for the deployment of whistleblowing as an accountability mechanism to curb corruption and fraud in a developing country. Nigeria is the institutional setting for the study. Nigeria's whistleblowing initiative targets all types of corruption, including corporate fraud. This study found that, even in the context of a developing country, whistleblowing is supported as an accountability mechanism, but the

Dependent Variable: GDP				
Method: Least Squares				
Date: 07/16/24 Time: 05:03				
Sample: 2003 2022				
Included observations: 20				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	135211.4	22106.43	6.116385	0.0000
RLF	-0.000126	4.80E-05	-2.637090	0.0167
R-squared	0.278680	Mean dependent var		84313.51
Adjusted R-squared	0.238607	S.D. dependent var		55241.37
S.E. of regression	48202.44	Akaike info criterion		24.49885
Sum squared resid	4.18E+10	Schwarz criterion		24.59842
Log likelihood	-242.9885	Hannan-Quinn criter.		24.51828
F-statistic	6.954246	Durbin-Watson stat		0.699792
Prob(F-statistic)	0.016739			

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intervention lacks awareness, presents a high risk to whistleblowers and regulators, including the risk of physical elimination, and is fraught with institutional and operational challenges.

METHODOLOGY

The ex-post factor research design was used for the study. The Ex post facto research provides a systematic and empirical solution to research problems, by using data which are already in existence. The sample period is 20 years from 2003-2022 and relies on secondary data collected from key agencies in Nigeria such as the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), the Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC), the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), and International organizations such as World Bank, IMF, UNDP, among others. The econometric view (E-view)

was used to analyze the transformed data. The ordinary least square was adopted for hypotheses testing. The following linear model guided the ordinary least square:

$$GDP/HDI = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4) \text{ ----- } 1$$

$$GDP = \alpha + \beta_1 RLF_{1t} + \dots + \epsilon_2$$

$$HDI = \alpha + \beta_1 RLF_{1t} + \dots + \epsilon_2$$

Where: GDP: Gross Domestic Product

HDI: Human Development Index

RLF: Recovery of Looted Funds

Ho₁: there is no significant relationship between recovery of looted funds and Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

INTERPRETATION OF OLS REGRESSION RESULTS

Intercept (C)

We found a coefficient (135211.4), showing the estimated value of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) when the recovered looted fund (RLF) is zero. This was associated with p-value (0.0000) and thus highly significant ($p < 0.01$), indicating that the intercept is statistically significant. This means there is strong evidence that the baseline level of GDP, when RLF is zero, is significantly different from zero.

Recovery of Looted Fund (RLF)

The result provided evidence of coefficient (-0.000126), suggesting a negative relationship between RLF and GDP. For every unit increase in RLF, GDP decreases by 0.000126 units. Given the small magnitude, this effect might not be practically significant, but it is worth noting. The coefficient was accompanied by p-value (0.0167) which is statistically significant at the 5% level ($p < 0.05$), indicating that there is strong evidence that RLF has an effect on GDP.

Model Fit

The model showcased R-squared (0.278680), thus indicating that approximately 27.87% of the variation in GDP is explained by the model, specifically by the recovered looted fund (RLF). This is a moderate R-squared value, suggesting that while the model captures a significant portion of the variance, there are still other

Dependent Variable: HDI				
Method: Least Squares				
Date: 07/16/24 Time: 04:58				
Sample: 2003 2022				
Included observations: 20				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.524730	0.012674	41.40169	0.0000
RLF	-5.30E-11	2.75E-11	-1.927611	0.0698
R-squared	0.171106	Mean dependent var		0.503400
Adjusted R-squared	0.125056	S.D. dependent var		0.029545
S.E. of regression	0.027636	Akaike info criterion		-4.244787
Sum squared resid	0.013747	Schwarz criterion		-4.145214
Log likelihood	44.44787	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-4.225349
F-statistic	3.715683	Durbin-Watson stat		0.441201
Prob(F-statistic)	0.069835			

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factors not included in the model that explain the majority of the variance in GDP.

Furthermore, the F-statistic (6.954246) and Prob(F-statistic) (0.016739), shows the overall significance of the model. The Prob(F-statistic) indicates the p-value for this test. At 0.016739, it is significant at the 5% level, suggesting that the model has explanatory power.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE FINDINGS

Economic Interpretation:

The negative coefficient for RLF suggests that increases in recovered looted funds are associated with decreases in GDP. This could imply that the process of recovering looted funds has a disruptive effect on the economy, possibly due to the costs associated with recovery efforts or a lack of effective reinvestment of these funds into productive activities.

The effect size, while statistically significant, is relatively small, so the practical impact on GDP might be limited but should not be ignored.

Ho₂: there is no significant relationship between recovery of looted funds and Human Development Index (HDI)

Interpretation of OLS Regression Results

From the result, we find the Intercept (C) with coefficient (0.524730), representing the estimated value of the Human Development Index (HDI) when the recovered looted fund (RLF) is zero. The p-value (0.0000) is highly significant ($p < 0.01$), indicating that the intercept is statistically significant. This means there is strong

evidence that the baseline level of HDI, when RLF is zero, is significantly different from zero.

Recovered Looted Fund (RLF)

We find a coefficient (-5.30E-11) suggesting a very small negative relationship between RLF and HDI. For every unit increase in RLF, HDI decreases by approximately 5.30E-11 units. Also, a p-value (0.0698), which is marginally significant at the 10% level ($0.05 < p < 0.10$). This suggests that there is some evidence, albeit weak, that RLF has an effect on HDI.

Model Fit

The result provided R-squared (0.171106) which indicates that approximately 17.11% of the variation in HDI is explained by the model, specifically by the recovered looted fund (RLF). This is a relatively low R-squared value, suggesting that there are other factors not included in the model that explain the majority of the variance in HDI.

F-statistic (3.715683) and Prob(F-statistic) (0.069835) The Prob(F-statistic) indicates the p-value for this test. At 0.069835, it is marginally significant at the 10% level, suggesting that the model has some explanatory power, though it is not strong.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study examined the relationship between whistleblowing and the Nigerian economy. Findings from the study showed that hypotheses one revealed that p-

value is (0.0000) and thus highly significant ($p < 0.01$), indicating that the intercept is statistically significant. The result further provided evidence of coefficient (-0.000126), suggesting a negative relationship between RLF and GDP.

The coefficient was accompanied by p-value (0.0167) which is statistically significant at the 5% level ($p < 0.05$), indicating that there is strong evidence that RLF has an effect on GDP. Furthermore, the F-statistic (6.954246) and Prob(F-statistic) (0.016739), shows the overall significance of the model. The Prob(F-statistic) indicates the p-value for this test. At 0.016739, it is significant at the 5% level, suggesting that the model has explanatory power.

The significance of RLF's impact on GDP suggests that while whistleblowing and the recovery of looted funds are important, they might have unintended negative consequences on economic performance. In summary, the study finds a statistically significant negative relationship between recovered looted funds and GDP, indicating that while efforts to recover looted funds are important, they may have adverse effects on the economy.

Hypotheses two showed that the p-value (0.0000) is highly significant ($p < 0.01$), indicating that the intercept is statistically significant. F-statistic (3.715683) and Prob(F-statistic) (0.069835) The Prob(F-statistic) indicates the p-value for this test. At 0.069835, it is marginally significant at the 10% level, suggesting that the model has some explanatory power, though it is not strong. The marginal significance of RLF's impact on HDI implies that while whistleblowing and the recovery of looted funds are important, they might not be sufficient alone to drive significant improvements in human development. In summary, while the study finds a statistically significant, though marginal, negative relationship between recovered looted funds and HDI, the practical significance is limited. This indicates that efforts to enhance human development in Nigeria should involve a multifaceted approach beyond just recovering looted funds.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Corruption is not a one-man affair especially in a country where corrupt elements are highly celebrated, and whistle blowing as machinery for fighting corruption is used to report corrupt act and wrongdoing voluntary for decisive legal procedure of punishing the culprit. The findings from the study revealed that recovery of looted funds is significantly related to GDP and Human Development Index. Based on these findings, the study recommends that:

1. Policymakers in Nigeria, should implement strategies to enhance recovery of looted fund, by ensuring

recovered funds are effectively and efficiently reinvested into the economy to support growth and development.

2. The Nigerian Government should improve the human development index in the country, by implementing a
3. multifaceted approach, beyond just recovering looted funds.

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